

FACTORS OF INFLUENCE ON NEW UZBEKISTAN-2030 ECONOMY

Sattarova N.T.

PhD, senior lecturer of department “Management”, SamIES

Abstract. In this article, the development process and stages of our country, the development trends of our country's economy, the impact of the New Uzbekistan-2030 strategy on the country's economy are studied by the author.

Key words: economy, business, household, New Uzbekistan-2030 Strategy, modernization.

“Uzbekistan – 2030” strategy is an important document that defines the important directions of the economic development of our country, and serves as an important program for the sustainability of our reforms to be implemented in the next seven years for the development of the country. In it, a number of priority tasks for ensuring employment and well-being of the population through sustainable economic growth are defined.

In our province, large-scale works are being carried out in the field of industrial development, in the process of attracting foreign investments to the economy, new enterprises are being launched and thousands of new jobs are being created. Unreasonable inspections of the activities of entrepreneurs and farmers, who are the electorate of the party, have been stopped, exporters have been encouraged, and business initiatives of young people and women are fully supported. As a result, the number of entrepreneurs increased sixfold, and local production developed. In our free country, the reforms to further liberalize

business activity based on the requirements of modern market relations, introduce a moratorium on various inspections, privatize enterprises, and limit state interference in the economy by supporting competition are highly effective.

At the initiative of the President, in order to increase the export potential of our region, increase the volume of production and maintain its quality at the level of world standards, and further improve cooperation with foreign investors, the "Uzbekistan GTL" plant was launched, the first synthetic oil in the history of the petrochemical industry of New Uzbekistan. production has been launched. The main goal is to increase the export potential of the sector by increasing the types of polymer products with high added value in exchange for deepening the processing of hydrocarbon raw materials and increasing the production of import-substituting materials.

It should be recognized that in recent years, 10 billion dollars of investment have been attracted to increase the economic potential of the region. The number of entrepreneurs has increased by 2.5 times, and 325,000 new jobs have been created. New projects have been put into practice, and the production of exportable products from local raw materials has been launched.

In the past seven years, the country's gross domestic product has increased from 52 billion dollars to 80 billion dollars, and this is an important indicator of the rapid development of our country. The strategy stipulates that a person who has committed a crime for the first time will be released from liability if he fully compensates the state for the damage caused to the state in the form of taxes and fees, including fines and other financial sanctions, before the court enters the consultation room. . From now on, during the investigation and trial of every criminal case brought against business entities, from the time when the relevant official accepts the materials of the criminal case, the business ombudsman, the Chamber of Commerce and Industry, as well as the business The introduction of the procedure for involving another organization as a public defender, of which

the subject is a member, is of great importance in ensuring the legal protection of entrepreneurs. Subsidy in the amount of 50 percent of the insurance premium will be a real help to the farmers of agricultural products in the insurance of the crop.

In order to support business, it is strictly guaranteed that the value added, profit, turnover and property tax rates will not be increased for business in the coming years, and starting from 2024, the population buying new housing and the value added tax will be reduced. half, 50 percent of the value tax is returned to farmers who sold agricultural products. The income tax of the employee will be refunded to the enterprises that employ residents entered in the social register. Businesses that pay taxes on time are given a one-day VAT refund period, and they are not subject to tax audits and are given priority in public procurement.

Due to the fact that the sustainability of the reforms is giving high results, the lifestyle and living conditions of our people are improving day by day, their way of thinking is changing and improving day by day. In a word, the "Uzbekistan-2030" strategy will serve as a program guide for us in our country to improve the economy, increase the employment and well-being of the population, and ensure the sustainability of the good works in the way of making people happy with life.

The priorities defined in this strategy impose great tasks on us in terms of creating conditions for entrepreneurs, implementing new projects, and helping to accelerate reforms. Our deputies and activists are carrying out explanatory and propaganda work on the implementation of party projects to develop local production in the region, to ensure employment of young people by directing them to entrepreneurship. The goal is to further develop the economic development of the oasis, to strengthen the confidence of our people in the future while ensuring stability, to accelerate the work for the development of our country, to provide a prosperous life to our people.

References

1. Мирзаев К.Ж., Пардаев М.Қ. Хизматлар соҳаси иқтисодиёти: Ўқув қуланма. Т.: «IQTISOD-MOLIYA». 2014. 384 б.
2. Голубицкая Е.А. Кухаренко Е.Г. Основы маркетинга и телекоммуникациях. – М.: Радио и связь, 2005. – 320 с.
3. Гончаренко Л.П. Инновационный менеджмент. 2-е изд., перераб. и доп. – М.: Юрат, 2014, - 640 с.